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THE CONCHOLOGICAL MAGAZINE

A MONTHLY

DEVOTED TO THE STUDY OF JAPANESE SHELLS.

Published By Y. HIRASE.

VOL. II.

DECEMBER, 1908.

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T H E
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No. 12

APPENDIX—ON JAPANESE MARINE MOLLUSCA (II),
WITH THE DESCRIPTIONS OF NEW SPECIES OF
MURICIDÆ AND BUCCINIDÆ

BY Y. HIRASE

MURICIDÆ.

Purpura hippocastaneum bitubercularis Lam. pl. xlii, fig. 252.

Tryon, Man. Conch. vol. ii, p. 162, pl. 45, fig. 36.

Jap. name, *Tsuno-tetsu-reishi* n. n.

Loc., Loo Choo and Suwanose-jima, Ōsumi.

Purpura tosana Pilsbry. pl. xli, fig. 241; pl. vi, figs. 45, 45a.

The figures were previously given to the public. But they were all imperfect; so I am obliged to put one of them in again.

Ussilla gouldii Smith. pl. xli, figs. 222-224; pl. vi, figs. 47, 47a.

The figures were previously given to the public. But they were all imperfect; so I am obliged to put them in again.

Sistrum alba Hombr. and Jacq. (?) pl. xli, figs. 245-247.

(Tryon, Man. Conch. vol. ii, p. 179, pl. 55, fig. 177.)

Jap. name, *Hime-shiro-reishidamashi* n. n.

Loc., Loo Choo.

Latiaxis pilsbryi Hir. n. sp. pl. xli, figs. 239, 240; pl. viii, figs. 64d, 64f.

Shell whitish, rather solid, funnel-shaped, broadly and perspectivally umbilicate, sharply carinate at the periphery and around the umbilical perforation. Spire flat or slightly convex, whorls $4\frac{3}{4}$, somewhat convex; suture rather deep, covered with a foliated carina; apex small and round. The body whorl flat above, tapering below; the carina slightly bending upward, continuous at the base, with 13-16 foliated

appendage; the appendage fragil, narrow-trigonal, consisting of doubled laminae, the laminae opened at the front but closed at the back, with one or two processes of growth wrinkles, showing that they are the relics of the transposed posterior canal. The umbilical carina has also 7-10 long and narrow semitubular, recurved appendage, continuous at the base and visible in the perforation, the inner the smaller. The both sides of the periphery and the part above the umbilical carina are concave, but the other part of the body whorl somewhat convex; the last one-third of the body whorl gradually descending. The detached aperture obliquely trigonal, the lower part tapering and receding, with a posterior canal on the upper part of the outer lip, and a long, recurved, spout-shaped anterior canal; the lip thin, but thickened within, slightly recurved, with a trace of some five teeth within. The surface smooth, sculptured irregular minute growth-lines and obscure spiral striae, running into the foliated shoulder carina.

The operculum dull reddish-brown, slightly curved, with a nucleus at the lower part of the outer margin.

a. Alt. (including the umbilical carina) 30, greater diam. 25, lesser diam. 20 mm.

b. Alt. (including the umbilical carina) 24.3, greater diam. 24, lesser diam. 18.5 mm.

a. Greater diam. 42.4, lesser diam. 30.3 mm. } including
b. " " 38.4, " " 27.8 mm. }

the peripheral carina.

Kashiwa-jima, Tosa; types in my collection.

At first I believed this peculiar precious specimen from the deep sea was a young *Latiaxis mawæ*, but since I have got three other such specimens and several true young *mawæ*, and have ascertained that these two are quite different. *L. pilsbryi* is distinguished from *mawæ* by the *lesser deflection of the body whorl in front, the foliated shoulder carina not so recurved, the sculpture not so coarse and the white surface without fresh tint.*

I am glad that I can have the honour of naming such a fine species in honour of Dr. Henry A. Pilsbry, to whom we owe almost all our knowledge of the Japanese shells.

Latiaxis spinosus n. sp. pl. xlii, figs. 253, 254.

Shell fusiform, narrowly umbilicated, whitish with longitudinal yellowish light brown stripes; spire long turrlicated. Whorls 8, the first rounded, forming a smooth protoconch, the rest angular in the middle convexly sloping above and below, with seven or more foliated spines at the angle, the spines curved upward and composed of doubled laminae, opened at the front irregularly dentated at the behind, and not continuous at the base. Suture rather deep with a series of shorter spines. The last angular at the periphery and little below, with 8 foliated spines at each angle, the lower shorter with more processes. The umbilicus encircled by about five short curved spines. The aperture rather small subcircular; lip thin, sharp, continuous, the columellar lip broadly expanded, the outer lip with two notches corresponding to the canals of the spines. Anterior canal moderate and recurved. Sculpture of distinct growth-lines and irregular spiral cords, coarser at the base.

Length (including the anterior canal) 25, diam. 13 mm., length of aperture 8 mm., length of the longest peripheral spine 8 mm.

Kashiwa-jima, Tosa; types in my collection.

Latiaxis tosanus n. sp. pl. xlii, figs. 255, 256.

Shell dull yellowish white, resembles to *L. japonica* Dkr., but remarkably smaller, with shorter spire and narrower shoulder appendages, tinted with light rose and not continuous at its base. Sculpture of spiral ribs with little spines (in *L. japonica* there are no spine on the dentated spiral lamellae), on the last whorl 4 or 5 ribs above and 6 below the periphery sometimes with smaller inter ribs, and always with fine striae. Whorls 7 or 8, protoconch lost; aperture semicircular, lip thin, the columellar lip free, inside of the outer lip with 11 revolving plicae.

Length 29, diam. 17.5 mm., diam. including the peripheral spines 25 mm.

Kashiwa-jima, Tosa; types in my collection.

This species differs from *L. japonica*, in color (*L. japonica* is pure white) and having numerous spines on the spiral ribs.

AQUILLIDÆ.

Aquillus (Lampusia) gemmatus Reeve. pl. xlii, figs. 258, 259.

Tryon, Man. Conch. vol. iii, p. 13, pl. 7, figs. 41-44.

Jap. name, *Shiro-shinomaki* n. n.

Loc., Loo Choo.

Aquillus (Lotorium) dunkeri Lischke. pl. xlii, fig. 257.

Lischke, Japanisches Meeres-Conchylien, i, p. 49, pl. 3, figs. 1, 2.

Tryon, Man. Conch. vol. iii, p. 19, pl. 11, fig. 82.

Jap. name, *Koshitaka-fujitsu* Iwakawa.

Loc., Awaji; Bōshu.

BUCCINIDÆ.

Chrysodonus intersculptus minor Hir. n. subsp. pl. xlii, fig. 263.

Shell yellowish white, closely resembles *C. intersculptus frater*, but much smaller with shorter spire, shallower suture, and shorter anterior canal. Whorls 6, apex wanted leaving $1\frac{1}{2}$ smooth protoconch; with weaker spiral ribs and fewer striæ, counting 5 or 6 between the ribs in the middle of the last whorl. The aperture with white thick callous within, the upper part of the outer lip thickened and slightly reflexed, the columellar lip with a thin callous and a subprotuberance near the posterior canal.

Length 70, diam. 43.5 mm., Length of aperture 41 mm.

Sagami (?); type in my collection.

Volutopsius hirasei Pilsbry. pl. xliii, figs. 264, 265.

Pilsbry, Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia, May, 1907, p. 243, pl. xix, fig. 2.

Jap. name, *Rikuzen-bora* n. n.

Loc., Kisen-numa, Rikuzen.

Beringius polynematicus Pils. pl. xliii, fig. 266.

Pilsbry, Proc. A. N. S. Phila., May, 1907, p. 243, pl. xix, fig. 1.

Jap. name, *Naga-bai* n. n.

Loc., Rikuzen: Kisen-numa.

Siphonalia mikado Melvill, Variety. pl. xliii, fig. 267.

Jap. name, *Hime-mikado-mikuri* n. n.

Loc., Kii.

Siphonalia kikaigashimana n. sp. pl. xlii, figs. 260-262.

The shell *smooth, glossy*, the spire elongated. Whorls $6\frac{1}{2}$, of which the earlier $1\frac{1}{2}$ protoconch, angular at the shoulder, convex in middle, but concave below the sutures, with 11 longitudinal folds, sometimes the earlier 4 whorls are free from them. Sculpture of ten or more fine spiral striae under the sutures, disappearing below the shoulder tubercles. Aperture semicircular, sinused at the upper angle, outer lip thin, submargined by short, close plicae within, inner lip thick colloused, basal canal strongly recurved.

Length 30.2, diam. 14.5, length of aperture 13 mm.

„ 29.3, „ 15, „ „ 14.5 „

Kikai-ga-shima, Ōsumi, types in my collection.

This white fossil species closely resembles *S. mikado* Melvill, but remarkably smaller with narrower last whorl, smoother surface and no nodule on the columellar lip near the posterior angle of the aperture. Original colour unknown.

Siphonalia cassidariaeformis tosana n. subsp. pl. xli, figs. 249-251.

Shell distinguished from *cassidariaeformis* by its smaller size, much shorter spire, larger last whorl, lower tubercles and in having longitudinal folds. Colour similar, but aperture light flesh within.

Length 32.2, diam. 20.3, length of aperture 18 mm.

„ 28.8, „ 20, „ „ 16 „

Kashiwa-jima, Tosa; types in my collection.

Siphonalia stearnsii Pilsbry. pl. xliii, fig. 268.

Pilsbry, Marine Mollusks of Japan, p. 29, pl. ii, figs. 1,2.

Jap. name, *Itomaki-mikuri* n. n.

Loc., Sagami (?).

Tritonidea erythrostroma Rve., Variety, pl. xli, fig. 248.

Tryon, Man. Conch. vol. iii, p. 155, pl. 73, fig. 246.

Jap. name, *Kuchi-beni-horadamashi* n. n.

Loc., Kikai-ga-shima.

ERRATA.

Vol. i, No. 12, p. 5. For "*Pecten yessoensis* Jay" read "*Fecten yessoensis* Jay."

Vol. ii, No. 1, p. 4. For "*Siphonalia pfeifferi* Sowb." read "*Siphonalia pfefferi* Sowb."

Vol. ii, No. 2, p. 7. For "*Arca granosa* Lischke" read "*Arca granosa* Linné."

Vol. ii, No. 9, p. 49, 7th line. For "Shing-king" read "Ch'eng-kan."

APPENDIX—ON JAPANESE LAND SHELLS (I)

- Macrochlamys serenus* Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 15-17.
 Jap. name, *Sukashi-bekkō* n. n.
 Loc., Kaminoyama, Uzen.
- Kaliella gudei mitsuensis* Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, fig. 23.
 Jap. name, *Mutsu-ōkibi* n. n.
 Loc., Osoreyama, Mutsu.
- Kaliella okiensis* Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 24-26.
 The Nautilus, vol. xxii, no. 4-5, p. 45.
 Jap. name, *Okinokuni-kibi* n. n.
 Loc., Nakamura, Oki.
- Kaliella subcrenulata satsumana* Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 27, 28.
 Jap. name, *Satsuma-hime-kasa-kibi* n. n.
 Loc., Yamakawa, Satsuma.
- Kaliella (?) boninensis* Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 31-33.
 Jap. name, *Ogasawara-kibi* n. n.
 Loc., Ani-jima, Ogasawara.
- Sitala ultima* Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 34, 35.
 Jap. name, *Uzen-shitara* n. n.
 Loc., Kaminoyama, Uzen ; Matsushima, Rikuzen.

REMARKS ON JAPANESE LAND SHELLS (VI)

- Microcystina tanegashimæ* Pils.
Macrochlamys tanegashimæ Pils. vol. 1, no. 12, pl. xii, figs. 116, 117.
Microcystina kumejimana Pils. and Hir. vol. 1, no. 10, pl. x, figs. 78, 79.
 By further study we have found that *kumejimana* is a synonym for *tanegashimæ*, and that both of them belongs to *Microcystina*.
 Loc., Tane-ga-shima ; Yaku-shima ; Kuchinoerabu-shima ; Toku-no-shima ; of Ōsumi ; Kagoshima ; Kuroshima ; of Satsuma ; Kume-jima, Loo Choo.

Macrochlamys subrejecta Pils. and Hir.

Macrochlamys rejecta Pfr., vol. ii, no. 1, pl. xiii, fig. 13.

M. rejecta is a Chinese species; Kobelt recorded it on the authority of A. Adams, who was apparently mistaken, so we must use the new name for the Tsushima and the Korean form.

NEW KOREAN ZONITIDÆ

Macrochlamys hypostilbe Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 15-17.

Jap. name, *Fusan-bekkō* n. n.

Loc., Fusan.

Macrochlamys quelpartensis Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, figs. 18, 19.

This journal no. xi, p. 63.

Jap. name, *Saishu-bekkō* n. n.

Loc., Cheju and Chongkori, Quelpart I.

Kaliella fusaniana Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, fig. 29.

Jap. name, *Fusan-kibi* n. n.

Loc., Fusan.

Kaliella obesicomus Pils. and Hir. pl. xxii, fig. 30.

Jap. name, *Chōsen-maru-kibi* n. n.

Loc., Kojetto.

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ERRATA—正 誤

P. 75. The Japanese name "Ogasawara-kibi" for *K. (?) boninensis* has been already named for *K. ogasawarana*, so that "Benin-kibi n. n." is to be named for *K. (?) boninensis*.

第二卷第十二號第四百五頁下段第二行“オガサハラキビ”は重複につきホニ
ンキビ平瀬と改稱す。

- | | | | |
|------|---|------|--|
| 15-} | <i>Macracliamys hypostilbe</i> Pils. & Hir. | 27-} | <i>Kaliella subcrenulata satsumana</i> P. & H. |
| 17-} | | 28-} | |
| 18-} | " <i>quelpartensis</i> Pils. & Hir. | 29. | " <i>fusiana</i> Pils. & Hir. |
| 19-} | | 30. | " <i>obesiconus</i> Pils. & Hir. |
| 20-} | " <i>serenus</i> Pils. & Hir. | 31-} | " (?) <i>boninensis</i> Pils. & Hir. |
| 22-} | | 33-} | |
| 23. | <i>Kaliella gudei mutsuensis</i> P. & H. | 34-} | <i>Sitala ultima</i> Pils. & Hir. |
| 24-} | | 35-} | |
| 26-} | " <i>okiensis</i> Pils. & Hir. | | |

264. } *Volutopsius hirasei* Pils.
265. }
266. *Beringius polynematicus* Pils.

267. *Siphonalia mikaŕo* Melv. var.
268. " *stearnsii* Pilsbry.

252.	<i>Purpura hippocastaneum bituberculare</i> Lam.	257.	<i>Aquillus dunkeri</i> Tschke.
253. }	<i>Latiaxis spinosus</i> Hir. n. sp.	258. }	" <i>gemmatus</i> Reeve.
254. }			
255. }			
256. }	" <i>tosanus</i> Hir. n. sp.	260. }	<i>Siphonalia kikaigashimana</i> Hir. n. sp.
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	263. <i>Chrysodomus intersculptus minor</i> Hir. n. subsp.		

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210. } *Latiaxis pilsbryi* Hir. n. sp.
211. } *Purpura tosana* Pils.
212. }
211. } *Usilla gouldii* Smith.

245. }
247. } *Sistrum alba* Hombr. & Jacq. (?)
248. } *Tritonidea erythrostoma* Rve., var.
249. }
251. } *Siphonalia cassidariformis*
 tosana Hir. n. subsp.